

Serabit el-Khadem: An Egyptian and Semitic Mining Community

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An interesting site in the Sinai frequented by both Semitic and Egyptian populations with evidence for worship of both Egyptian and Semitic deities. It is most interesting for three factors: 1) its existence as a turquoise mine, 2) its temple to Hathor which exists for multiple centuries, is renovated, and eventually contains an addition to Sopedu, and 3) the existence of Proto-Sinaitic alphabetic inscriptions related to Semitic peoples and deities. The Hathor temple is initially built in the Middle Kingdom, presumably over an original cave dedicated to Hathor. Hathor eventually becomes associated with turquoise, as seen by her epithets in inscriptions at the site. Perhaps due to this development, significant additions to the temple were undertaken during the Late Bronze Age under the reigns of Thutmose III, Hatshepsut, Amenhotep II, Thutmose IV, and Amenhotep III, while inscriptions bearing the names of Ramesses II, Ramesses IV, and Ramesses VI convey their interest in the site. For historical reconstructions, Hathor's name is also important as it gradually loses the foreign land determinative. As I have argued elsewhere, a shift of assumption occurs in that the Egyptians at the site are no longer worshipping in a foreign land. Instead, the land has ideologically become a part of Egypt. Simply put, the foreign land determinative is no longer used because the Egyptians no longer consider Serabit el-Khadem to be part of a foreign land. The religious importance of the site may predate Egyptian presence, with the site perhaps initially connected to a Semitic deity. The numerous hieroglyphic inscriptions at the site do little to clarify the picture. The possible existence of an earlier Semitic cult, likely dedicated to Baalat, arises from a small corpus of ~40 Proto-Sinaitic inscriptions, dating roughly to 1700-1400 BCE and presumably inscribed by the native Semitic workers at the site, of which at least 5 contain the name of the goddess. These inscriptions were originally published by Alan Gardiner in 1916, and the interpretation of b'lt as Baalat has largely remained accepted. The content of the inscriptions, however, does little to clarify the nature of Semitic worship at the site. The inscriptions are short and dedicatory in nature, although they do convey that other Semitic deities, such as Teššub, were also worshipped at the site.

Date Range: 1900 BCE - 1200 BCE

Region: Serabit

Region tags: Egyptian Desert

Sinai; Egypt

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ventura, R. “The Egyptian Temple at Sarabit El-Khadim.” Sinai Part 2, edited by G. Gevitzman and Et.al., Tel Aviv, 1987, p. (Heb.).
- Source 2: Giveon, R. “Lady of the Turquoise: Hathor at Serabit El-Khadim and Timna.” The Impact of Egypt on Canaan: Iconographical and Related Studies, edited by R. Giveon, Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1978, pp. 61-67.
- Source 3: Giveon, R. “Investigations in the Egyptian Mining Centres in Sinai.” Tel Aviv, vol. 1, 1974, pp. 100-108.

Notes: Also, see, Thompson, S. Displays of Cultural Hegemony and Counter-Hegemony in the Late Bronze and Iron Age Levant: The Public Presence of Foreign Powers and Local Resistance. Routledge, 2023.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: N/A

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The site has been excavated and revisited numerous times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Years of excavation:

– Year range: The site has been excavated and revisited numerous times.

Notes: Serabit el-Khadem in the Sinai was initially excavated in 1905 by Flinders Petrie, revisited in 1935 by Jaroslav Černý with a focus on the inscriptions, and finally studied from 1968-1978 by a team from Tel Aviv University led by Raphael Giveon

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Multiple excavations

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Turquoise Mine

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: Extensive Mining Activity

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: It is in the middle of the Sinai Peninsula and extremely remote.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: It is in the middle of the Sinai Peninsula and extremely remote.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: There were likely caravan routes..

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: It is likely on/near established caravan routes.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: I point here to the temple of Hathor. It was likely originally built over a cave dedicated to Hathor. This cave was, potentially, originally dedicated to a Semitic deity - likely Baalat.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Turquoise Mine

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: There were dwellings for the miners.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: There were multiple construction stages, beginning the Middle Bronze. Significant additions to the temple were undertaken during the Late Bronze Age under the reigns of Thutmose III, Hatshepsut, Amenhotep II, Thutmose IV, and Amenhotep III. 1998 A Grammar of Epigraphic Hebrew. Atlanta: Scholars Press.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Originally built in the Middle Kingdom and refurbished to last into the New Kingdom.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: There are still significant material remains at the site, but no modern reconstruction has been attempted. This is likely due to its remote location.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Hathor

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: Not dedicated but there is evidence of the worship of Baalat and Tesub at the site.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: Likely commissioned and renovated by Egyptian pharaohs.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely built by either the miners or by professionals.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Likely sponsored by the Egyptian government.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: Hathor was an extremely popular deity in ancient Egypt who gave many gifts to those who worshiped her.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Hathor is associated with the turquoise mine. She is referred to at the site as "Lady of the Turquoise."

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: A temple of Sopedu was added in the New Kingdom.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Hathor Temple is the most important structure.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: The temple is relatively simple and serves little more than its direct purpose. I would not consider it "monumental." It is relatively large, covering about 2800 sq. meters, and about 80 m in length.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: Most prominent are representations of Hathor in bovid form.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Field doesn't know

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:
– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There were likely paintings and the reliefs were likely painted.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions at Serabit are the most prominently studied feature of the site. While many are directly associated with the temple and are written in hieroglyphs, the most important inscriptions are more often studied for their linguistic importance, rather than their content. I hear reference the small corpus of ~40 Proto-Sinaitic inscriptions, dating roughly to 1700-1400 BCE and presumably inscribed by the native Semitic workers at the site, of which at least 5 contain the name of the goddess Baalat. They do not shed any light on actual Semitic worship at the site, other than the inclusion of deity names.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: I would not consider Hathor or Sopedu to be a "supreme high god."

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Traditional Egyptian religion would suggest that the cult objects could be inhabited by

the divine.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: I would consider Hathor and Sopedu as physically being able to inhabit this place.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

Notes: I have said "yes" here as well because the religious specialists can act as a proxy for the pharaoh.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: We do not have this cult statue but we can assume it was present.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

- ↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
 - No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

- No

Are material offerings present:

- Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - No

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

- No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

- Yes

- ↳ Is it required:
 - Yes

Notes: Based on comparative evidence for Hathor worship, it would be required.

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - Yes

Notes: Based on comparative evidence for Hathor worship, it would be required.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There is at least one major reconstruction, at which time a shrine to Sopedu was added. The initial temple to Hathor is also built on top of an original Cave of Hathor.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is probably that there was some permanent temple staff, but it could have been a short term position given its remote location.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is probable that there were religious festivals held at the temple given the lack of other options.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably, but not 100%.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: No idea

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: No idea

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely, but not 100%.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The same rules would apply as apply elsewhere in Egypt.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is a strange site as there would not have been permanent inhabitants among the workers.

Bedouin would have lived in the region but there is really nothing else to control other than the mines.

They may have been in charge of food distribution.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is highly likely but not 100%. There would really be no other location to serve as a place for food distribution.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Perhaps. The inscriptions are the most interesting part of the site though, with both Semitic and Egyptian religion present.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Scriptures is not an accurate term to use here, but I will say "yes." There are Proto-Sinaitic inscriptions related to this site.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– No

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Serabit el-Khadem: An Egyptian and Semitic Mining Community, Ventura, R.. "The Egyptian temple at Serabit el-Khadim". In *Sinai part 2*, edited by G. Gervitzman. Tel Aviv, 1987.

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